

Extended report on the outcomes of a Virtual Mobility

Action number: CA18235

Grantee name: Horatiu Stefanie

Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca

horatiu.stefanie@ubbcluj.ro.

Virtual Mobility Details

Title: *Transfer of expertise for QA (Quality Assurance) tests and data processing using the ATLAS tool to be applied by the station in Cluj, Romania*

Start and end date: 14/10/2023 to 29/10/2023

The Cluj Atmospheric Remote sensing Observatory is composed of a young remote sensing team operating a LR231-D300 multi-wavelength Raman depolarization LIDAR and recently joined the ACTRIS network. Lidar instruments operating in the framework of the European Network ACTRIS-Aerosol, Clouds, Trace Gases Research infrastructure (<https://www.actris.eu/>) are required to perform standard quality assurance tests and calibrations and this implies an a priori knowledge on the current quality assurance QA protocols used within ACTRIS. In addition, a new software used to test the QA tests was developed in the framework of CARS (Center for Aerosol Remote Sensing).

The ATLAS software is a python based code developed by the ACTRIS Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing to be used at the ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing National Facilities as the standard software for in house lidar calibration. The software covers the analysis of the Rayleigh signals, telecover and depolarization calibration tests. In order to use Atlas, the user must fill in two configuration files designed to cover the additional input required to understand and process the raw lidar data. These files include information on the detected channels, information about the site, radiosounding and the Single Calculus Chain SCC configuration. During this VMG, the Cluj operators were trained on how to fill in the configuration files. Several iterations were required to debug the setup files and to optimize the lidar acquisition in providing a correct data header that will be later used to process the lidar raw data.

Description of the activities carried out within the VM.

1. Optimizing the lidar instrument

The first issue solved within the VMG was the correct setup of the detection channels: laser assignment for each channel and the correct definition of the depolarization channels (initially

reversed).

About the QA tests: Telecover.

Deviations of near range signals from different parts of the telescope and the comparison of such deviations of different lidar channels and with theoretical ray-tracing simulations can reveal the distance of full overlap and possible reasons for the deviations from the ideal case.

In the near range region, we do not have a calibration method for a lidar system, where almost never clean air conditions can be assumed. But shortcomings of the optical and opto-mechanical design or misalignments have their largest effect in the near range. A test for this range is based on the fact that the backscattered photons collected by different parts of the telescope of a lidar system must give the same range dependency of the partial signals, and if not, the range dependency of the whole signal is uncertain. With ray tracing simulations we see that ray bundles collected by different telescope parts reach the signal detector in different paths through the optical receiver and hit the optical components under different incident angles with possibly different transmission. Possible causes for the differences are laser tilt, telescope misalignments, displacement of field and aperture stops. The geometrical overlap function, which is mainly determined by the size and location of the telescope's field stop, is just the most obvious feature producing differences in different telecover signals. (Freudenthaler, V., et al., 2018)

The telescope can be covered in a way that just quarters of the telescope are used, which we call the Quadrant-test (see Fig. 3), or using only an inner and outer ring of the telescope, i.e. the In-Out-test. Using In-Out sections of the quadrants is called the Octant-test. With an ideal lidar system the normalized signals from all different telecover tests must match - apart from the overlap range, which can be therewith assessed, and assuming constant atmospheric conditions during the test.

Fig 1: Nomenclature of the telecover parts (plot at right) with respect to the laser position at North (biaxial systems) or any prominent orientation of the receiver optics (mono-axial systems). Using the four quarters N, E, S, and W in the left picture is called the quadrant test. Using the outer and inner parts of the quadrants is called the octant test. The pictures above show (from left to right) the sectors North (N), North-Out (NO), North-In (NI), Full-Out (FO), and Full-In (FI) on a telescope, assuming the laser on top (based on Freudenthaler, V., et al., 2017)

The first set of QA tests indicated a serious misalignment of the south sector for 0355xpar. The South sector, the sector placed opposite to the emission axes should have the lowest signal intensity. Results from the first Telecover indicated that for the normalized signals, the South profile has a much stronger intensity compared to the rest. The relative deviation plot also indicates a strong difference between the south and the other sections. Usually this is caused by either wrong misalignment of the emission/receiver unit or by bad placement of the telescope aperture. Discussions with the INOE team lead to two solutions: first try to improve the alignment of the emission and then, if this is not efficient, try to adjust the telescope aperture. The instrument has a computer controlled alignment based on piezo-electric motors. Online meetings between INOE and CLUJ were setup to solve the issue. The alignment was

carried out by INOE, with the help of CLUJ. After optimizing the overlap, the CLUJ operators covered each sector of the telescope and INOE operators performed online optimization for each sector.

Fig 2: First telecover test

Once the alignment was finalized, the CLUJ operators performed some additional QA tests to check the alignment.

Fig 3: Second telecover test

The result of the test indicated that the South intensity issue was caused by a wrong misalignment of the emission and that the problem was corrected.

Another aspect indicated by the telecover tests was related to the presence of an additional pattern in the lidar signal – seen here for altitudes around 1.5 – 2.5 km. This is usually caused by the presence of strong electromagnetic sources or ground loops. INOE technicians had to visit CLUJ in order to try to identify possible sources. The first test was to isolate the detection unit from the laser power supply.

Fig 4: Electronic pattern in the signal

The new set of telecover tests indicated that the approach was correct and the pattern was significantly reduced. The relative deviation indicates that all signal agree within the 0.05 limit for altitudes above 300 m.

Fig 5: Corrected pattern in the signal

About the QA tests: Polarization Calibration.

The calculation of the volume linear depolarization ratio profile (VLDR) and particle linear depolarization ratio profile (PLDR) requires calibration of the polarization sensitive lidar channels; In order to be able to perform a polarization calibration, the AHL must be equipped with a polarization calibration module.

The calibration of polarization channels is specific to each lidar system but the basic principles are similar for most of the instruments. The calibration of the polarization channels consists of assessing the measured calibration factor and then applying all necessary corrections to reduce the contribution of the instrument.

A reliable solution for calibrating the polarization measurements is represented by the 45° calibration. This calibration implements a 45° rotation of the polarization analyzer (PBS and the PMTs) with respect to the polarization plane of the laser in order to equalize the light intensity in the cross and parallel channels. When comparing the calibration signals, the ratio between the transmitted and reflected signals reflects the contribution of optics and

electronics in the lidar receiving unit. The main source of uncertainty involved in this kind of calibration is represented by the accuracy which determines the 45° rotation with respect to the true zero position of the PBS. A more advanced solution is to use two subsequent measurements taken by rotating the polarization analyzer at $\pm 45^\circ$ with respect to the default measuring position (David, et al., 2012). This calibration is called the “ $\pm 45^\circ$ calibration”. The calibration constant is determined by using the geometric mean of the two $\pm 45^\circ$ measurements. The two measurements are designed to compensate each other even for cases in which the 45° rotation uncertainty is large with respect to the initial zero position given by the PBS (Freudenthaler et al., 2009).

Results from the CLUJ instrument indicate that the setup of the parallel and cross 532 nm channels is wrong. Results for the measured and corrected volume depolarization products indicated values of 60 instead of 0 to 0.5. First possible cause is the wrong wiring of the depolarization channel. Second issue to be considered is wrong rotation of the polarization cube. Online meetings were scheduled to perform a complete rewiring of the signal cables.

Fig 6: Results for the measured and corrected volume depolarization products

Fig 7: Results for the measured and corrected volume depolarization products after optimization

The new set of QA tests indicate improved values for the linear volume depolarization ratio.

About the QA tests: Far range alignment.

The comparison of lidar signals in clean air ranges with the signals calculated from air density and temperature profiles from radiosondes is the only absolute calibration of lidar signals. To be able to calibrate lidar signals with the so-called Rayleigh (molecular) backscatter signals, the optoelectronic detection systems must have a high dynamic range.

The Rayleigh-fit is a normalization of the range corrected lidar signal to the calculated attenuated molecular backscatter coefficient (β_m attn, Rayleigh signal) in a range where we assume clean air without aerosols and where the calculated signal fits the lidar signal within the noise limits.

Results for the far range alignment test (Rayleigh) indicate also a wrong alignment of the

emission.

Fig 8: Far range alignment for 0355xcat - missalignment

After the online alignment, the new set of QA tests indicate correct lidar signals up to 10 km.

Fig 9: Far range alignment for 0355xcat – correct alignment

The test data indicates that after optimization, the operation of the instrument was significantly improved. Similar results were obtained for the depolarization channels. The test data indicates a significant improvement after the optimization.

ATLAS was used to test the first set of QA tests. Based on the results of this test, several iterations were required to debug the lidar instrument and improve its operation.

The online sessions held together with the INOE team were aiming to reduce the presence of the electronic noise and to improve the alignment of the instrument. After two online sessions on how to optimize the wire layout and on how to perform the near range alignment, the second session of telecover test showed a significant improvement.

2. Optimizing the lidar data processing

The second phase of the VMG was based on the operational configurations of the Single Calculus Chain SCC. Together with the Bucharest team, the Cluj team managed to setup the nighttime configuration and bypass the gluing errors returned by the HIRELP module and also managed to solve all ELDA errors.

First step of the setup process was to create new dedicated configurations for daytime and night time.

Id	Lidar version	Configuration Name	Station (owner)	PI	Locked Configuration	Automatic upload to EARLINET database
78	30: COLI - Version 1.0	always	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
274	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	daytime	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
275	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	nighttime	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
331	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	dep_cat_VIS	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
662	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	CLOP_daytime_2022	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
663	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	CLOP_nighttime_2022	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
748	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	CLOP_daytime_2023	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✔
749	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	CLOP_nighttime_2023	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✔
750	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	dep_cat_VIS_2023	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖
775	29: CLOP - Version 1.0	dep_cat_UV_2023	cj	Nicolae Ajtai	✖	✖

Fig 10: SCC lidar configurations for CLUJ

The daytime configuration “CLOP_daytime_2023” was setup to include elastic backscatter products for 532, 355 and 1064 nm and depolarization products for 532 and 355 nm.

System/product connections	
product id	
2268	ID: 2268 elast. backscatter (usecase: 4) at 355.0000 nm
2269	ID: 2269 elast. backscatter (usecase: 4) at 532.0000 nm
2260	ID: 2260 elast. backscatter (usecase: 0) at 1064.0000 nm
2270	ID: 2270 Elastic Backscatter and Linear Depolarization Ratio (usecase: 1) at 532.0000 nm
2337	ID: 2337 Elastic Backscatter and Linear Depolarization Ratio (usecase: 1) at 355.0000 nm

Fig 11: SCC lidar products for daytime configuration CLUJ

The configuration was setup in parallel to the depolarization calibration measurements performed together with the INOE station. These measurements were submitted to the SCC to be included in the assessment of the depolarization products.

The night time configuration included two additional products related to the Raman extinction channels.

System/product connections	
product id	
2260	ID: 2260 elast. backscatter (usecase: 0) at 1064.0000 nm
2268	ID: 2268 elast. backscatter (usecase: 4) at 355.0000 nm
2269	ID: 2269 elast. backscatter (usecase: 4) at 532.0000 nm
2263	ID: 2263 Raman backscatter (usecase: 11) at 355.0000 nm
2264	ID: 2264 Raman backscatter (usecase: 9) at 532.0000 nm
2270	ID: 2270 Elastic Backscatter and Linear Depolarization Ratio (usecase: 1) at 532.0000 nm
2337	ID: 2337 Elastic Backscatter and Linear Depolarization Ratio (usecase: 1) at 355.0000 nm

Fig 12: SCC lidar products for night time configuration CLUJ

Once the setup was completed, the QA tests were used to assess the initial parameters for the SCC configuration. These parameters were provided within the CARS report for the CLUJ

station.

Parameters retrieved from the tests

Channels		Minimum product height <i>based on Telecover Test</i>	Maximum product height <i>based on Rayleigh Fit</i>	Dead time <i>based on PI info</i>	First signal range bin <i>based on Zero bin test</i>	Trigger delay <i>based on Zero bin test</i>
ATLAS ID	SCC ID	[km]	[km]	[ms]	[bins]	[ms]
0355xpar	2172	0.3	14.5	3.06	1021	
0355xppr	2173				1011	
0355xcat	2235				1017	
0355xcpt	2236	0.3	14.5	3.06	1014	
0387xvbn	2174				1021	
0387xvan	2175	0.3	20	3.06	1011	
0532xcat	2178				1021	
0532xcpt	2177	0.3	12.5	3.06	1011	
0532xpar	2180				1020	
0532xppr	2179	0.3	11.5	3.06	1011	
0608xvbn	2176				1012	
1064xtax	2171	0.4	8		1022	

Channels		Pol. cross-talk parameters		Correction factor for pol. cal.	VLDR systematic error
ATLAS ID	SCC ID	G	H	K	
0355xcat/ 0355xcpt	2235/2236	1	-0.9999	1	0.0005
0355xpar/ 0355xppr	2172/2173	1	1	1	0.0005
0532xcat/ 0532xcpt	2178/2177	1	-0.999	1	0.0021
0532xpar/ 0532xppr	2180/2179	1	0.999	1	0.0021

The next phase of the work is related to the provision of newly collected data to test the current configuration in strong collaboration with the INOE station.

Conclusions:

The VMG was a great opportunity to setup online meetings focused on debugging the lidar instrument in Cluj. These meetings were focused on: a) optimising the cable layout to suppress electronic noise seen in all lidar channels; b) correcting the channel setup for the depolarization products; c) solving the header info errors related to the laser assignment; d) preparing the configuration files for the ATLAS software; e) running the ATLAS software to test the QA data; f) performing a real time, online alignment to optimize the near range signals; g) testing the SCC configurations and correcting the channel and products setup; h) creating a centralized online summary of all operational configurations for the Cluj station in order to keep track of all parameters used in SCC (current and future updates).

The VMG was a great opportunity to connect to the Bucharest station for the optimization and operation of the Cluj instrument. The correct operation of the instrument based on the QA will help the Cluj team (lead by Horatiu Stefanie) to better control the quality of the raw lidar data and allows calculating the instrumental parameters which are further used in the processing chain. The ATLAS software was set for Cluj and run to analyse the QA test data. The results of the QA were discussed to better understand the output of ATLAS. A full report was submitted by CARS based on the optimization performed during the VMG.

All the work was carried out remotely, using virtual platforms with regular discussions between the participants. All tests were performed by the Cluj station but remotely supervised by Livio Belegante (INOE, Bucharest, Romania- ACTRIS/CARS- Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing representative). The alignment of the lidar was carried out remotely by the representative of the Bucharest station together with the direct participation of Cluj operators. Additional training sessions will be carried out between Bucharest and Cluj for better usage of the ATLAS software.

The VM achieved its planned goals and expected outcomes, including specific contribution to Action objective (1) 'Capacity building for end-users through training and demonstration on the use and impact of ABL products in multiple applications for societal benefit' and (2) "Research coordination- Improve the capabilities of existing ABL instrument networks through (a) the design of harmonized data and metadata formats, real-time processing, optimal measurement strategy building on existing network implementation experience"- Objective O4.1. This VM has contributed to the COST excellence and inclusiveness policy,

due to this action involved researchers from an Inclusiveness Target Country (ITC)- Romania;
The transfer of expertise carried out in the VMG adds a valuable contribution for studies related to atmospheric aerosol from high power lidar instrumentation.